

Performance of elite basmati rice varieties of subtropical India under temperate valley conditions of Kashmir

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India is one of the largest exporters of basmati rice in the world, in addition to being home to a large number of quality rice varieties, both aromatic and nonaromatic. With the growing demand for aromatic rice locally and abroad, there is a need to introduce such varieties into the agriculture-based economy of Kashmir Valley. Traditionally, however, Kashmir farmers do not grow basmati varieties partly because they do not like long-grain flaky rice and partly because these varieties have low yield and late maturity under the valley's temperate and high-altitude conditions. In the last few years, there were efforts to develop and popularize basmati and fine-grain aromatic rice in the region, with acceptable physicochemical, cooking, and eating qualities and 140-d growth duration.

To determine the potential of using elite rice introduced directly in Kashmir, six aromatic basmati varieties/hybrids released for the subtropical areas of northern India – Pusa Sugandh 3, Pusa Sugandh 5, Pusa 2517-2-51-1, UPR2268-5-1, HKR 2K-603, and Ranbir Basmati – were tested under transplanted and irrigated conditions at the RRSS (33.73°N, 75.15°E, 1,601 m asl). The varieties in 10-m² plots were evaluated using a randomized complete block design with three replications. Two indigenous aromatic rice types of Kashmir Valley (Mushk budji and Kamad) were used as checks. The existence of these local landraces has been documented for more than a century (Lawrence 1895) and they have been maintained by farmers ever since (Parray and Shikari 2008).

These basmati varieties were evaluated for adaptability, yield, and milling, cooking, and eating characteristics. The acceptable ranges of physicochemical parameters for premium-quality basmati rice were as follows (Anonymous 2005): kernel length greater than 6.6 mm and breadth less than 2 mm; alkali spreading value between 4 and 5 on a 1–7 scale; kernel length after cooking and kernel elongation ratio of not less than 12 mm and 1.70, respectively; intermediate amylose (20–25%) preferably with soft gel consistency values; and volume expansion ratio greater than or equal to 3. In our experiment, we found that Pusa Sugandh 3 satisfied all these criteria, followed by Pusa Sugandh 5 (Table 1).

Table 1. Grain quality characteristics of rice varieties.

Characteristic ^a	Pusa Sugandh 3	Pusa Sugandh 5	Pusa 2517-2-51-1	UPR2268-5-1	HKR 2K-603	Ranbir Basmati	Kamad	Mushk Budji	CD (0.5%)
Amylose content (%)	26.78	29.42	26.16	25.20	20.38	22.29	18.42	14.53	1.21
Gel consistency (mm)	60.23	55.71	50.44	64.10	90.43	75.33	87.28	90.85	9.81
Alkali spreading value	5	7	6	6	5	5	3	4	0.70
Kernel length (mm)	7.56	8.23	7.50	7.49	7.18	6.86	5.52	4.75	0.96
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.80	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.25	1.75	2.50	2.51	0.82
Length-breadth ratio	4.20	4.70	4.29	4.28	5.74	3.92	2.21	1.89	0.44
Kernel length (after cooking) (mm)	15.23	17.00	12.41	11.20	11.53	10.55	8.75	7.50	2.30
Kernel elongation ratio	1.98	2.07	1.66	1.47	1.61	1.53	1.59	1.58	0.31
Volume expansion ratio	4.39	4.41	3.14	3.50	4.38	3.14	3.16	2.94	0.30
Aroma (after cooking)	5	5	3	4	3	4	3	3	0.55
Kernel shape	Long slender	Long slender	Long slender	Long slender	Long slender	Long slender	Medium slender	Short bold	-

^aAll traits were measured according to the IRRI Standard evaluation system for rice (1996).

Significant differences have been observed, with Pusa Sugandh 5 recording the highest amylose content (29.42%), followed by Pusa Sugandh 3 and Pusa 2517-2-51-1. Pusa Sugandh 3, Pusa Sugandh 5, and Pusa 2517-2-51-1 showed medium to hard gel consistency, while the others showed soft gel consistency. An intermediate alkali spreading value of 5, which is desirable and is indicative of gelatinization temperature in the range of 70–74 °C (beyond which starch granules change their structure irreversibly, resulting in cooked rice kernels), was found for Pusa Sugandh 3 and Ranbir Basmati. Pusa Sugandh 5 and Pusa Sugandh 3 had the highest kernel length values, kernel elongation ratio, and volume expansion ratio. As expected from their high amylose and medium-hard gels, these varieties had well-separated kernels and became moderately hard to hard upon cooling. Very low amylose content for Mushk Budji and moderate aroma for Kamad in comparison with Pusa Sugandh 3 were noted. Mushk Budji had short bold kernels and Kamad had medium slender ones; all others had long slender grains.

Among all aromatic rice varieties, Mushk Budji was the earliest to mature (126 days after sowing, DAS), whereas, among the basmati types, Pusa Sugandh 3 matured earliest (147 DAS) (Table 2). HKR 2K-603 and Ranbir Basmati did not mature at all. Basmati rice UPR2268-5-1 showed 55.1% and 67.7% yield superiority over checks Mushk Budji and Kamad, respectively. However, since it matures a fortnight late (154 DAS), local farmers may not adopt it because its maturity coincides with the onset of the wet season and results in a subsequent delay in sowing of the rabi crop. The consequence is a shortage of labor for harvesting. On the other hand, Pusa Sugandh 3 matures in 147 DAS and has a grain yield of 6.2 t ha⁻¹, good aroma after cooking, high amylose, intermediate alkali spreading value, and medium gel consistency. This fine-grain, scented restorer line of wild-abortive cytoplasm, with desirable quality features comparable with those of Taroari Basmati and Pusa Basmati 1, and moderate resistance to blast, is a promising variety for Kashmir as it has been for traditional basmati-growing areas of Punjab, Haryana, Delhi, Uttaranchal, and western Uttar Pradesh.

Table 2. Yield performance of six different basmati genotypes vis-à-vis two local aromatic landraces, RRRS, Khudwani, J&K, India, 2007 kharif.

Variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Percent increase over check	
							1	2
Pusa Sugandh 3	IET16313-Pusa 2504-1-31 (basmati restorer line)	103.9	114.7	146.7	312.4	6.2	43.6	55.2
Pusa Sugandh 5	Pusa 1121	103.4	118.3	150.0	299.2	5.7	30.8	41.3
UPR2268-5-1	UPR908-11-1-1-5/A8342B	99.7	114.3	154.0	396.0	6.7	55.1	67.7
HKR 2K-603	IET4141/HBC19//HBC19	106.0	120.3	DNM ^a	261.8	DNM ^a	–	–
Pusa 2517-2-551-1	P1238/P2504	101.4	116.0	152.0	323.4	5.7	30.8	41.3
Ranbir Basmati	Selection from Basmati 370	105.7	121.7	DNM ^a	287.1	DNM ^a	–	–
Mushk Budji (check 1)	Local landrace	105.3	94.0	125.7	181.5	4.3	–	–
Kamad (check 2)	Local landrace	101.4	102.5	135.5	173.2	4.0	–	–
CD (5%)		13.33	2.21	1.54	21.32	12.7		
CV (%)		4.14	1.13	0.61	4.30	13.0		

^aDNM = the variety did not mature.

References

- Anonymous. 2005. Laboratory manual on rice grain quality procedures. In: Training for Officials of Export Instruction Council of India. New Delhi (India): Directorate of Rice Research. p 14-17.
- Lawrence WR. 1895. The Valley of Kashmir. London: Frowde H. 463 p.
- Parray GA, Shikari AB. 2008. Benefit-cost ratio in producing aromatic and non-aromatic rice genotypes in Kashmir Valley. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 32(2):38-39.